

Quantum Spatial Probability and Time Intervals in the High Energy Limit

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 6, 2021

Linking quantum mechanics to classical mechanics seems to have been an early goal in quantum theory as represented by the correspondence principle. More recently there have been attempts to link the entropy of both a single bound quantum state and a thermal statistical system of quantum states to classical entropies (1),(2). For the former, the entropy is proportional to $\int dx \text{density}(x) \ln[\text{density}(x)]$ where $\text{density}(x) = \Delta t = 1 / v(x)$ with $v(x)$ being velocity. Thus, density, which is a probability in Shannon's entropy equation, is a measure of the change in the value of $\Delta t(x)$ in this classical entropy. Bound state quantum mechanics is said to be time-independent, but by the correspondence principle (1) the probability of the envelope of the wavefunction i.e. $\text{Envelope}(W(x)) \cdot \text{Envelope}(W(x)) = \Delta t(x)$ so quantum probability (albeit linked to the envelope) is related to classical time intervals which adjust with x to yield the proper relation $v(x) = \Delta x / \Delta t(x)$ with Δx being constant.

In this note we argue that the expectation value: $\int W(x) d/dx dW/dx = \int WW KE_{\text{classical}}(x)$ for a bound state is, in the high energy limit $\int dt KE_{\text{classical}}(x)$ i.e. a portion of the action, just as in the classical case (i.e. the correspondence principle). This leads to the association of the higher energy limit of the envelope of W times itself with $\Delta t(x)$.

Classical Action

The classical action is given by:

$$\int dt L \quad \text{where } L = T - V \text{ (usually) } T \text{ being kinetic energy and } V \text{ potential ((1))}$$

What is interesting, we argue, is that the presence of dt suggests equally spaced constant dt units, just as $\int f(x) dx$ suggests equally spaced dx units. Given that velocity changes in time (i.e. also in space) one cannot have both dx and dt remain constant because:

$$v(x) = dx/dt \quad ((2))$$

One choice is to use $dt(x)$ so that slices in time vary with x in order to create the correct velocity. If one consider the portion of the action:

$$\int dt .5 m v(x)v(x) \quad ((3)) \text{ with this choice then this is equivalent to:}$$

$$\int .5m dx v(x) = .5 \int dx p(x) \quad ((4))$$

We argue that a correspondence principle linking quantum bound states to classical mechanics should satisfy ((3)) because the action ultimately governs classical motion.

Classical Entropy for a Bound State

In (1), classical entropy for a bound state is given by Shannon's formula:

$$S = b \int dx \text{density}(x) \ln[\text{density}(x)] \quad ((5))$$
 where b is a constant

$\text{density}(x)$ is a probability related to x and is chosen in (1) to be $dt(x)$. We argue that classical mechanics is deterministic and so does not seem to have any probability. It seems that one considers the variation in $dt(x)$ with x compared to a constant dt as a kind of probability. Mathematically $dt(x)$ is a distribution over x resulting from a change of $dt = \text{constant}$ and probability theory deals with such distributions. Nevertheless, the Shannon's probability in this scenario must be considered as somewhat different from usual probabilities as it is not really linked with uncertainty which seems to be a main feature of the idea of probability. Given that classical mechanics is deterministic one knows exactly the value of $dt(x)$ at x . It is just that one has a distribution instead of $dt = \text{constant}$.

Link with Quantum Bound States

Quantum mechanics on the other hand deals with "usual" probabilities i.e. $W^*(x)W(x)$ is the probability to find a particle at x . It is also, however, a distribution over x as compared to a constant probability for all x . This holds even in the case of constant $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ i.e. a particle in a box. For a quantum bound state, time is removed (or is only present in $\exp(-iEt)$), so dx is considered to be constant throughout x . Nevertheless:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W = \text{KE classical}(x) \quad ((6))$$

As a result, there is a $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ value which follows from derivatives of the wavefunction and is linked to $dx = \text{constant}$ and $dt(x)$. Thus there is a link between the wavefunction (which is further linked to spatial probability) and $dt(x)$. It is just not clear how to make this link more explicit. It seems that the correspondence principle which relates high energy bound states to classical physics may be used to achieve this goal.

We consider the expectation value:

$$\int dx W(x)W(x) \text{KEclassical}(x) \quad ((7))$$

Here dx is a constant over x , but $W(x)W(x)$ is the bound state probability for the particle to be at x . We argue that in the high energy limit ((7)) should behave like a classical portion of action (which governs classical motion). Thus ((7)) is equivalent to:

$$\int dt \text{KE classical}(x) \text{ which implies that } W(x)W(x) = 1/v_{\text{rms}}(x) \quad ((8))$$

If dx is constant then $v_{\text{rms}}(x) = dx/dt(x)$ so $W(x)W(x)$ is directly linked to $dt(x)$ i.e. the distribution over x of time slices in the classical picture or the v_{rms} quantum picture. It is actually the envelope of $W(x)W(x)$ which should be used because quantum mechanics is based on periodic

$\exp(ipx)$ type representations which remain in the high energy quantum limit, but do not appear in the classical case. Using an envelope which roughly touches the quantum wavefunction peaks allows for the quantum density to be linked to the classical $1/v_{rms}(x)$ value.

Implications

As a result, a stochastic theory such as bound state quantum mechanics, with a spatial probability $W(x)W(x)$ is linked to a deterministic theory by considering its relationship with a $dt(x)$ distribution over x . In other words, the quantum particle has different envelope $W(x)W(x)$ values (in the high energy limit) in order to create the classical $dt(x)$ distribution if the correspondence principle is to hold. Looked at this way, $W(x)W(x)$ (for a bound state) does not appear so much as a probability, but rather as a distribution needed to modify a constant dx and give rise to the variable distribution $dt(x)$ which also does not appear to be a probability. Nevertheless, $dt(x)$ is used as a probability in Shannon's entropy in order to calculate an entropy for a bound classical state. In (1), the classical entropy equation is used to determine information about high energy quantum entropy.

Conclusion

The correspondence principle links quantum mechanics to classical mechanics in the high energy quantum limit. Quantum mechanics, however, is a statistical theory (based on probabilities) while classical mechanics is deterministic. (In addition, quantum mechanics is based on $\exp(ipx)$ wave-like motion which does not disappear even in the classical limit and is not found in usual classical motion. This aspect, however, is not considered in the correspondence principle as one examines an envelope of $W(x)W(x)$ the quantum spatial probability.)

One may ask how a statistical theory, even in the high energy limit, may be linked to a deterministic one. It seems that given that $v(x)$, where v is velocity in the classical case, one has a distribution $dt(x)$ over x because time slices must change with x if $dx = \text{constant}$. One would normally think of $dt = \text{constant}$, but this must be adjusted into a distribution over x to handle $v(x)$. If one insists that the quantum expectation value: $\int dx W(x)W(x) KE_{classical}(x)$ where $KE_{classical}(x) = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ be the first part of the classical action $\int dt KE_{classical}$ in the high energy limit then $dx W(x)W(x) = 1/v_{rms}(x)$ where $v_{rms} = dx(\text{constant})/dt(x)$. Thus quantum probability $W(x)W(x)$ is linked to varying $dt(x)$ (time slices). In other words, the quantum particle in the high energy limit must change its distribution in space in order to convert $dx W(x)W(x)$ into the classical $dt(x)$. As a result, neither $W(x)W(x)$ nor $dt(x)$ really look like probabilities (which suggest uncertainties), but serve rather as distributions over x .

References

1. Majernick V. and Richterick L. Entropic Uncertainty Relations (1999)
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231009385_Entropic_uncertainty_relations
2. Campisi, M. On a New Definition of Quantum Entropy (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/0803.0282.pdf>